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Abstract

Gender pay gap is phenomenally global. It manifests in different dimensions, across borders and has spanned centuries. However, increasingly insatiable drive to achieve steady and viable economic growth ignited extensive research on gender issues. The study examined nexus of gender pay gap and economic growth in Nigeria. By employing data from both public and private sector of Nigerian economy during period 2005-2012, estimation was done using OLS regression method. The result indicates a significant positive relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth. Hence, pay structure should be implemented strategically with much gender sensitivity to benefit economy

Key words: Pay Gap, Human Capital Endowment, Economic growth

1. Introduction

In recent time, increasingly insatiable drive to achieve steady and viable economic growth has extended research focus on gender issues. Contemporary researchers have recognized the pivotal role of gender issues for achieving macroeconomic objectives and found that gender difference in earnings (i.e. gender pay gap) have cost and benefit implications on macroeconomic objectives (Cavalcanti & Tavares, 2007; Esteve-Volart, 2009; Oostendorp, 2009). Gender pay gap is phenomenally global. It manifests in different dimensions, across borders and has spanned centuries. While a longer finger is pointed to emerging countries, the developed countries are still in the struggle of narrowing this gap. Although pace of narrowing this gap differs among countries of the

World, developing countries have established to have the widest gender pay gap (ILO, 2009).

Nigeria is one of the developing countries with the widest gender pay gap: there is still wide gap in wage or income generating and employment opportunities of women and men in almost all sectors especially industrial sector where the gap is pronouncedly evident as a result of social and perceptive constructs on some economic activities (Oyelere, 2007; UNDP, 2011). However, human beings are rational, irrespective of the gender connotation, inability to satisfy fundamental needs through engagement in productive activities result in disincentive to work or lack of self-fulfillment and regrettable consequential reduction in aggregate productivity and overtly or covertly negate expected performances of macroeconomic variables in an economy (Oginni, 2013).

Series of studies exist on gender issues especially on access to education, properties and other assets, but few studies were carried out on gender pay gap and economic growth (Lagerlöf, 2003; Busse & Spielmann, 2005; Weichselbaumer & Winter-Ebmer, 2005; Baliaoune-Lutz and McGillivray, 2007; Blau & Kahn, 2007; Mitra-Kahn, 2009). Some studies established positive relationship while others a negative relationship; hence there were mixed evidences. Given the central place of economic growth in an economy, there is no research to date which has examined this in Nigeria context. Thus, this study sought to examine this empirically.

2. Literature Review

Recent studies across disciplines such as public policy, gender studies, economics, policy and human rights have focused much attention on pay gaps created by gender characteristics. Some studies have presented convincing evidences on the existence of gender pay gap demonstrated at different pace across the World (Schober & Winter-Ebmer, 2009; Lamanna, 2009; Seguin, 2010; Kabeer & Natali, 2013).

Gender pay gap connotes gender discriminations exhibited in the reward for labour: wages, salaries or any earning from productive efforts (EC, 2007; Thomas & Winter-Ember, 2009). In other words, gender pay gap is the earning differences between women and men in paid employment in the labour market. Fapohunda (2013) opines that gender pay gap has to do with the relative differences in the average gross earnings of men and women within an economy. In this study, focus is on gap created by gender orientation/characteristics despite equal productive of the labour in the marketplace. For example, if Mr. 'A' has equal productivity as Mrs. 'B' and Mrs. 'B' is paid lesser than Mr. 'A' by the reason of

being female, then there is gender pay gap (Figure 1). Besides gender orientation/characteristics which is direct discrimination, other determinants of gender pay gap include human capital endowments (Walby & Olsen, 2002) and labour market related-institutions and complexes such as occupational segregation (Grimshaw & Rubery, 2002; Watts, 2003), industrial segregation (Drolet, 2001, Eastough & Miller, 2004; Cassells et al., 2008), public-private sector effects (Miller, 2005; Kee, 2006), firm size (Mitra, 2003; ABS, 2008) and personality traits (Fortin, 2008).

Figure 1: Pay Gap created by gender characteristics.

Source: Authors (2014)

While human capital endowment is found negligible determinants of gender pay gap in some studies, elsewhere the gap is attributed to difference in human capital endowments (Eastough and Miller 2004; Kee, 2006; Preston 2000; Cassells, Vidgattama, Maranti & McNamara, 2009). Cassells *et al.* (2009), using robust microeconomic modeling techniques, found that simply being female is the main contributing factor to pay gap in Australia; that if the effects of being female were removed, the average wage of an Australian woman would be more than men. Similarly, Kee (2006) found that the difference in return to gender characteristics instead of differences in endowments is the most important determinants of gender pay gap. However, Forsythe, Korzeiniewicz and Durant (2000) opines that discrepancies between the gender in employment and pay structure are primarily results from human capital differences which are consequences of traditional structures likely to disappear over time.

3. Relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth

Empirically, there are mixed views on the relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth. Cabegin (2012) examines widening of gender wage gap in economic slowdown of the Philippines and found that gender pay gap is sensitive to economic conditions: it contracts with accelerated economic growth and widens with a deceleration in growth; that men earned more than

women in service and construction sectors but removal of gender discriminations against women would increase their earnings more than men’s. Similarly, Cavalcanti and Tavares (2007) posit that a higher gender pay gap leads to lower output per capital: as gender pay gap decreases, the disadvantaged gender work more as result of added pay premium, and thus GDP per capital increases, *ceteris paribus*.

However, Seguíno (2000) examined twenty semi-industrialized export-oriented economics to explore relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth. She found that gender gap in manufacturing earnings was positively associated with economic growth, mainly through its positive effect on exports and investments. Elsewhere, using the same data employed in Seguíno (2000) and inclusion of some additional variables, relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth was found to be either zero or negative (Schober & Winter-Ebmer, 2009), although this was subsequently objected in Seguíno (2011) for wrong measurement and variable inclusion.

Mitra-Kahn and Mitra Kahn (2009) investigate the relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth of export-oriented semi-industrialised countries and found that the relationship varies across countries and is dependent on level of industrialization. Mitra-Kahn et al. (2009) found a positive quadratic relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth in the countries that depend on low-skill export manufacturing while in high-skill export manufacturing, this relationship inverts: even gender pay gaps are no longer associated with higher growth but some wage discrimination. Furthermore, they found that as countries grow, this optimal level of wage discrimination then moves towards 0. This study is unique in that it would provide, for the first time, empirical quantitative evidence of the nexus of gender pay gaps and economic growth in Nigeria during period 2005-2012.

4.0 Empirical Model

Following Blinder-Oaxaca (1973), wage or pay model was developed as follows:

$$P_{gi} = \beta_g X_{gi} + \varepsilon_{gi} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where P_{gi} is the log wage/pay and is a vector of control characteristics of an individual i of g_i . The aggregate pay gap between the gender (i.e. men and women) is decomposed into endowment effect (effect of different productive characteristics, denotes as E) and discrimination effects (unexplained residual denotes as U). Thus, the mean pay differential can be written as:
 $\bar{P}_m - \bar{P}_f = (\bar{X}_m - \bar{X}_f) \hat{\beta}_m + (\hat{\beta}_m - \hat{\beta}_f) \bar{X}_f = E + U \dots (2)$

Where W_{gi} and X_{gi} denote the mean log pay/wage and control characteristics of group g and β_g denotes the vector of estimated parameters from equation (1). However, this study emphasizes the relationship between genders pay gap and economic growth, the function for economic growth rate ($\Delta\text{Log}Y$) is written as follows (Seguino, 2000; Schober et al., 2009):

$$d\text{Log} Y = \alpha + \gamma_1 d\text{Log} K + \gamma_2 LE + \gamma_3 Gini + \gamma_4 HC + \gamma_5 \text{gender_pg} + \mu \dots (3)$$

Where $d\text{Log}K$ is the growth rate of the capital stock proxy as the growth rate of gross fixed capital formation; Gini Coefficient ($Gini$), Life expectancy rate (LE), human capital represented by HDI . Focus of this study is on coefficients measures of the gender pay gap ($gender_pg$), which takes 1 when there is gender pay, otherwise 0.

Data employed for this study was obtained from UNESCO (2012), World Bank, World Human Development Report (2013) and CBN (2013). It covers some selected sectors of Nigerian economy: public and private sector for the period 2005-2012. Analysis was performed using Gretl Econometric Software.

5.0 Estimation Results

Table 1-2 presents estimation results of the nexus of gender pay gap and economic growth using Ordinary Least Square regression. Capital growth stock ($\text{logcapitalgrowstock}$), life expectancy ($life_exp$), Gini co-efficient ($Gini$), human capital (HDI), gender pay gap ($gender_pay_gap$) in both public and private sectors formed independent variables and dependent variable was economic growth (logEcgrowth). All variables tested were found statistically significant at 5% and 1% (F -statistics (20112.2; $p < 0.01$).

Table 1: OLS Regression Result (Model 1)
Dependent Variable: LogEcgrowth

Variable	Coefficients	Significance (p-value)	t-statistic
Const	0.638	<0.00001***	14.2569
Logcapgrowstock	1.606	<0.00001***	200.288
Life_exp	-0.001	0.00022***	-3.8905
Gini	-0.012	<0.00001***	-7.0398
HDI	0.8689	<0.00001***	7.6107
Gender_pay_gap	0.0239	<0.00001***	15.0501
F-statistics (5,74) = 20112.1 (p-value <0.00001)			
Unadjusted $R^2 = 0.9261$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.9211$			

*** Significant at 5% and 1%.
Source: Authors' Computation (Gretl Output)

Under Model 1 (Table 1) explanatory variables influence economic growth rate by 92.6% as indicated by adjusted R^2 (0.926), *ceteris paribus*. Capital growth stock (logcapgrowstock) shows significant positive relationship while life expectancy rate ($life_exp$) reflects a negative relationship. In reality, a steady growth of gross fixed capital stock enhances economic growth while low life expectancy rate affects productive working populations and hence economic growth. It seems that a statistically significant positive relationship was found between gender pay gap and economic growth in Nigeria: 0.01% widening of the gap brings about a corresponding rise of economic growth rate, other factors remain constant. The result is similar to Seguino (2000) who found such positive relationship in semi-industrialized export-oriented economics through its effect on exports and investments. Also, Mitra-Kahn et al. (2009) found a positive but quadratic relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth in the same export-oriented economics.

Table 2 (Model 2) presents estimation result on the relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth in both private and public sectors of Nigeria.

Table 2: OLS Regression Result (Model 2)
Dependent Variable: LogEcgrowth

Variable	Coefficients	Significance (p-value)	t-statistic
Const	2.087	<0.001***	29.0161
Logcapitalgrowthstock	1.205	<0.001***	20.9701
Life_exp	-0.22	<0.001***	-8.5274
Gini	-0.04	<0.001***	-7.1296
HDI	22.91	<0.001***	8.0143
Gender_pg_PubSec	-1.85	<0.001***	-8.6273
Gender_pg_PrivSec	1.806	<0.001***	8.5460
F-statistics (6,73) = 15569 (p-value <0.00001)			
Unadjusted $R^2 = 0.999219$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.999155$			

*** Significant at 5% and 1%.
Source: Authors' Computation (Gretl Output)

Explanatory variables influence economic growth to the tune of 95% as indicated by *adjusted R²* (0.9495), *ceteris paribus*. This implies fixed capital stock, life expectancy rate, Gini coefficient, human capital and existence of gender pay gap in both private and public sector cause economic growth to change significantly. For every 1% growth of fixed capital stock, economic growth rises by 1% and for every 1.10% rise in human development

index economic growth rate is raised by 1.10%. However, in Nigerian public sector, a significant negative relationship was observed between gender pay gap and economic growth: 0.99% widening of the gap causes economic growth rise by 0.99%, *ceteris paribus*. Also, gender pay gap in Nigerian private sector showed a significant positive relationship with economic growth rate: 1.01% widening of the gap raises economic growth rate by 1.01%. Interestingly, when contribution of public sector to economic growth corresponds to private sector, the effect of gender pay gap on economic growth will be neutralized, other factors influencing economic growth are held constant.

5.0 Conclusion

Gender pay gap is phenomenally global. It manifests in different dimensions, across borders and has spanned centuries. However, the increasingly insatiable drive to achieve steady and viable economic growth has extended research focus on gender issues and it was discovered that gender pay gap has cost and benefit implications in achieving macroeconomic objectives. The result of the study indicates a significant positive relationship between gender pay gap and economic growth in Nigeria.

Comparatively, in public sector a significant negative relationship was observed compared to private sector where a significant positive relationship was found. Nonetheless, based on results of this study, if contributions of both sector of the economy (private and public) are the same, then effect of gender pay gap on economic growth will be zero. Hence, pay structure in both private and public sector should be strategically implemented (with gender sensitivity) to benefit economy.

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Table 3: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Dev.
Ecgrowth	6.61	6.81	3.44	8.21	1.35
Cap_grwstock	14.04	8.80	-19.89	59.39	27.22
Life_exp	51.49	50.58	48.66	60.12	3.42
Gini	3.25	3.00	3.00	4.00	0.44
HDI	0.45	0.46	0.43	0.47	0.01
Public_Sec	0.50	0.50	0.00	1.00	0.50
Private_Sec	0.63	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.49
Gender_pay	0.25	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.44

Source: Authors' Computation (Gretl Output)

Table 4: Variable Description

	Variables	Description
Dependent	LogEcgrowth	Logarithm of Economic Growth
Independent variables	Logcapitalgrowthstock	Logarithm of capital growth stock
	Life_exp	Life expectancy
	Gini	Gini co-efficient
	HDI	Human Development Index
	Gender_pay_gap	Gender pay gap which takes 1 if there is gap, otherwise 0
	Gender_pay_gap_PublicSec	Gender pay gap in public sector which takes 1 if there is a gap, otherwise 0.
	Gender_pay_gap_PrivateSec	Gender pay gap in private sector which takes 1 if there is a gap, otherwise 0.